

Appendix A: Process Metrics for UC2 at the case company

Process Factor ^a	Process Metric	Description
Development Speed	Daily build performance	Density of daily builds with duration below the defined threshold
	Automated Testing Performance	Density of automated tests with duration below the defined threshold
	Commit Response Performance	Density of commits with duration below the defined threshold
	Commit Review Performance	Density of commit reviews with duration below the defined threshold
	Commit Review Iterations	Density of commits with number of iterations below the defined threshold
Testing Performance	Error Correction Performance	Density of errors corrected with duration below the defined threshold
	Error Identification Performance	Density of errors identified in a given timeframe
Issues Velocity	Old Issues	Density of issues of a given priority older than the defined creation threshold
	Resolved Issues	Density of issues resolved in a timeframe
	Resolved Issues' Throughput	Density of resolved issues with lifetime below the defined threshold
	Team Throughput	Density of issues resolved in a given timeframe

^a Process factor is an attribute of part of a process that is concrete enough to be measured. The underlying process metrics, collectively, help to measure each process factor

Appendix B: Thematic synthesis of the feedback interviews

Higher-order Theme	Theme	Illustrative Text
Helpful concept	Help with data availability	That metric has been collected...yeah, that is the main thing for us
		I think, especially the one about, if data is being collected at all. That's very important. We've had problems, that there was no data.
	Fine concept	It's an important metric, yes... I like the concept. Maybe, it's like "Maturity" or something. In any case, it's important to measure it The main principles are very good.
Validation mechanism	Support quality	Yes, because that is getting the big picture, that how our project is doing...work and quality
		If we get the metrics there correctly, and we have the data...so that will give information about our process quality, and we can do software in a more quality manner.
	Validate instinct and reality	I think it's it is very useful I think. Because right now, you see a...indicator saying something like product quality is 0.4, or something like that. There's kind of lack of a way to know how closely it matches the real situation....I think it's important, yes.
		So, for me, it's important in a way to...I'll be able to judge whether metrics are reflecting reality myself. So, maybe the reliability thing is great for, kind of, giving confirmation that my own instinct is correct, and also when showing to the managers. I have something to support my own ideas. So, I mean, some metrics...the reliability metrics is there to support my views.
Helpful indicator	It's true that end user won't have such deep knowledge of the system. So, yes, it's good for them to have some indication of how reliable the metric is	
Actionable - Effectiveness - Trustworthiness	Trust	If influences me such that we can trust that metrics, and we can set up those action points to our sprint work, and do those alerts.
	Impactful	I see it (impact) because when I was checking those simulations, and those metrics, I saw that in one...when we...little bit changed that...and then I checked what were the metrics behind that, so there was that...straight impact to our daily work.
		Impacts in a good range
		That is very impactful. Currently, it is quite unclear which metrics are reliable,,
	Usefulness	I guess the answer is that, if there is no indication that they are reliable, that's...that's not very good, that brings down the usefulness
Decision-making	I think if we can be sure they are reliable, and we can use them to make decisions more, and more, So it is important. So...so the more reliable we know that they are, the more we can base our decisions on the metrics.	
Larger Scope - Transparent	Process reliability	Developers have to work according to our processes, and we get reliability for that, that we are doing things correctly, and that we can trust those metrics
	Visibility	I think if they can...if they get more information about how the reliability is calculated, then they can see, why it's so...why it's not 100%. That might be important